

CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE WITH NEUROLOGICAL COMPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) often suffer from neurological complications. These complications have the potential to affect both the central and peripheral nervous system. Common neurological complications in CKD include stroke, cognitive dysfunction, encephalopathy, peripheral and autonomic neuropathy. These conditions have a significant impact not only on patient morbidity but also on mortality risk through a variety of mechanisms. Understanding the pathophysiological mechanisms of these conditions can provide insight into effective treatment strategies for neurological complications.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, neurological complications, uremic neuropathy, uremic encephalopathy, cognitive dysfunction, peripheral neuropathy, autonomic neuropathy.

Relevance. This review describes the clinical management of neurological complications in CKD with reference to associated physiological and pathological disorders. Stroke, cognitive dysfunction and dementia share several pathological mechanisms that may contribute to vascular dysfunction and neurodegeneration. Cognitive dysfunction and dementia can be differentiated from encephalopathy, which has similar factors but is acute and rapidly progressive and may be accompanied by tremor and asterixis. Recent evidence suggests that restricting potassium intake with food may be a useful preventive measure for peripheral neuropathy. Treatment of painful neuropathic symptoms can be achieved with pharmacological agents, with careful dosage selection and consideration of side-effects with regard to reduced renal function. Patients with autonomic neuropathy may respond to sildenafil for impotence. Neurological complications often become clinically evident in the terminal stage of the disease. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a serious global health problem with a prevalence of about 15% in developed countries. CKD is defined as a decline in kidney function that persists for three months or more and spans the disease continuum from mild kidney damage to end-stage disease. The severity of the

disease is classified according to a five-stage system based on the calculated glomerular filtration rate (rGFR), a calculation of the waste products excreted by the kidneys per minute. The etiology of CKD can be due to primary renal disease or to a complication of a multisystem disease associated with comorbidities, such as diabetes, which is currently the leading cause of CKD worldwide. Regardless of the cause, neurological complications are common in CKD. Damage can occur at all levels of the nervous system, including central nervous system (CNS) disorders such as stroke, cognitive dysfunction and encephalopathy, through to peripheral nervous system (PNS) conditions such as autonomic and peripheral neuropathies. The presence of these complications has a significant impact on patient morbidity and mortality.

Conclusions: Thus, the clinical management of neurological complications in CKD requires an understanding of the concomitant physiological and pathological abnormalities. While neurological complications often manifest clinically at the terminal stage of the disease, identifying and treating these conditions early in CKD may reduce their impact at later stages. This review will discuss common neurological complications in CKD with reference to their functional manifestations, classified as 'altered mental status' or 'physical disability'. Possible causes of these functional impairments will then be discussed, along with current recommendations for clinical care.

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